

PARTICULAR CHARACTERISTICS OF SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION

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Abstract: *The current article is devoted to the particular theoretical views of simultaneous interpretation. Many scholars view interpreting as a form of translation. Based on that assumption, interpreting studies are expected to benefit from the theory and research in the field of translation. However, interpreting studies has benefited from translation studies only to a very limited degree. Therefore, particular characteristics of simultaneous interpretation require to be investigated in details prior to analyzing them in practical sense. Interpreting is commonly believed to be one of the most cognitively demanding language tasks. Simultaneous interpreting, also involves processes and skills such as: self-monitoring, memory skills, verbal fluency and concurrent listening and production. In order to provide a high-quality interpretation, the interpreter needs to master all of these above-mentioned skills. The question of interpreters' aptitude has been widely discussed in the context of this article.*

Key words: *Synchronic, aptitude, complexity, Pragmatic-linguistic, Socio-pragmatic competence, smooth delivery, International Association of Consultant Interpreters – IACI, European Commission Joint Interpreting and Conference Service – JICS*

Аннотация: *Настоящая статья посвящена отдельным теоретическим взглядам на синхронный перевод. Многие ученые рассматривают устный перевод как форму перевода. Исходя из этого предположения, ожидается, что исследования устного перевода выиграют от теории и исследований в области перевода. Тем не менее, переводческие исследования извлекли выгоду из переводческих исследований лишь в очень ограниченной степени. Поэтому конкретные характеристики синхронного перевода требуют детального изучения, прежде чем анализировать их в практическом смысле. Устный перевод обычно считается одной из самых сложных языковых задач с точки зрения познавательных способностей. Синхронный перевод также включает в себя процессы и навыки, такие как: самоконтроль, навыки памяти, беглость речи и одновременное слушание и*

производство. Для обеспечения качественного устного перевода переводчику необходимо владеть всеми вышеперечисленными навыками. Вопрос о способностях переводчиков широко обсуждался в контексте данной статьи.

Ключевые слова: синхронность, способность, сложность, прагматико-лингвистическая, социопрагматическая компетентность, бесперебойная доставка, Международная ассоциация переводчиков-консультантов, Объединенная служба устного перевода и конференций Европейской комиссии.

Annotatsiya: Joriy maqola sinxron tarjimaning alohida nazariy qarashlariga bag'ishlangan. Ko'pgina olimlar tarjimani tarjimaning bir ko'rinishi deb bilishadi. Ushbu taxminga asoslanib, tarjimonlik tadqiqotlari tarjima sohasidagi nazariya va tadqiqotlardan foyda olishi kutilmoqda. Biroq, tarjimashunoslik sohasi so'nggi yillarda juda cheklangan darajada olg'a siljidi. Shu sababli, sinxron tarjimaning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini amaliy jihatdan tahlil qilishdan oldin ularni batafsil o'rganish kerakligi muhim vazifalardan biri sifatida ko'rilmogda. Tarjimonlik kognitiv jihatdan eng talabchan til vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Sinxron tarjima, shuningdek, o'z-o'zini nazorat qilish, xotira qobiliyatlari, og'zaki ravonlik va bir vaqtda tinglash va ishlab chiqarish kabi jarayonlar va ko'nikmalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Yuqori sifatli tarjimani ta'minlash uchun tarjimon yuqorida aytib o'tilgan barcha ko'nikmalarni egallashi kerak. Tarjimonlarning qobiliyatlari masalasi ushbu maqola doirasida keng muhokama qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Sinxronik, qobiliyat, murakkablik, Pragmatik-lingvistik, Ijtimoiy-pragmatik kompetensiya, muammosiz yetkazib berish, Xalqaro maslahatchi tarjimonlar assotsiatsiyasi, Yevropa Komissiyasining qo'shma tarjimonlik va konferensiya xizmati.

One of the most particular characteristics of simultaneous interpretation is effectiveness, which is really tough to acquire by interpreters. The process is regarded very challenging because the time between original speech and translated speech comprises only three or four seconds. It means that a speaker utters his/her words without stopping and meanwhile, an interpreter must translate the words simultaneously. During this hard procedure, the memory, the rich vocabulary and wide outlook of an interpreter occupy a very crucial importance to successfully accomplish this arduous task. Despite of these above mentioned difficulties, more than 90% of international conferences are held with the greater presence of simultaneous interpreters. Moreover, simultaneous interpretation embraces very huge scientific and

specific characteristics. Therefore, it demands tremendously high requirements from future interpreters as it is widely used during official conferences and interpreters have no right to commit even a single tiny mistake. Main requirements which are asked to interpreters go as follows: firstly, while the original speech is being uttered, simultaneous interpreter must differentiate every single detail by listening very carefully. Furthermore, by relying on the thematic knowledge, they must predict the text that goes in the original speech and through perceiving and memorizing the date they must deliver the information accurately. The most complicated part of the process is that above mentioned steps happen in a very short period. Besides that, the ability of dexterous thinking and high-quality verbality is immensely impartial for interpreters during international conferences and official meetings. As Atkinson, Richard C. and Richard M. Shiffrin [1] stated According to the resolution of IACI (International Association of Consultant Interpreters), if a simultaneous interpreter can translate the speech of a speaker at 80% (as it is impossible to realize a 90-100% interpretation process), it is considered a successful interpretation process. According to Bartłomiejczyk, [2] sometimes, the speech of some conference participants is very fast; therefore it is very difficult for interpreters to keep up with the pace of the speakers' speech and this complicates the work of interpreters.

Gile, Daniel [3] exemplified that speakers usually perplex interpreters even more by using dialect words and idioms during their speeches. In such cases, interpreters have to accelerate all of their treasure of knowledge and falling behind their experience, they have to show their power. It is a pity that there are very few people who speak slowly in order to facilitate the work of interpreters.

According to Anderson, R. B. [4] It is not an easy work to deal with simultaneous interpretation. In addition, people who work in this profession must possess certain high qualities and features. In the interpretation competency, simultaneous interpreters must have the following three qualities which are counted as the most essential ones.

1) Linguistic ability. It comprises of pragmatic competence, in its turn, pragmatic competence is divided into two types.

a) Pragmatic-linguistic competence – according to scholars' opinions, interpreter must know the particular features of certain words and phrases.

b) Socio-pragmatic competence. It means to recognize the functional methods and etiquette and other things that occur in simultaneous interpretation.

2) General understanding. It is the quality with the help of which interpreters are able to build up their special vocabulary relying on their general knowledge about certain topics. In this case, interpreters will be able to accomplish their task without any difficulty.

3) The skill of smooth delivery. The quality with the help of which, interpreters are able to deliver the interpretation relying on their secret strategies.

Howard, Ian [5] considered the activity of simultaneous interpretation to be the peak of oral translation process. That's why there are very high demands on the preparation of interpreters. Any kind of simultaneous interpreters who wants to succeed must possess the following skills:

- 1) The ability of speaking fluently both in source and target language.
- 2) The speech which is built up in high grammatically and phonetically developed manner.
- 3) Rich vocabulary in both source and target language.
- 4) The ability of quick recognizing and finding all kinds of difficult phrase-logical words and clichés.
- 5) The ability of interpreting correctly and effectively both in source and target language.
- 6) The ability of swift reaction.
- 7) Firm operative memory.
- 8) Highly-focused concentration.
- 9) Mental and physical stamina.
- 10) The ability of working in groups.
- 11) The ability of possessing encyclopedic knowledge.

Dam, Helle V. [6] clarified in his notes that there is not any organization or union that controls the misunderstandings or mistakes which are done at conferences, therefore, the motto of simultaneous interpretation is “only success and no mistake”. After the conferences finish, the delegates, participants and the chief of conference usually express their gratitude to interpreters. If the work done by interpreters is purely-perfect, a lot of credits and applauses are directed to them and everybody tries to work with them again next time. If the interpretation is very poor, there will be several reactions created by the participants such as, chatting with each other, tapping their feet or coughing and many other undesirable situations. It is not appropriate to neglect even a tiny detail during interpretation process. As the microphone in the booth is very sensitive, interpreters must be very careful when they are moving. Even a single sound of turning the pages of

papers or books and the sound of earrings worn by female interpreters may go through sensitive microphones as a loud noise.

According to Diriker, E, [7] there are several international organizations for accrediting the skills of simultaneous interpreters. One of the famous one is International Association of Consultant Interpreters – IACI, which was founded in 1953, the knowledge of the members of this association is ranked very high and acknowledged by many other international organizations. There is no need for any examination to get enrolled into this association. In order to be one of the members of this organization, one must need a two-year experience as an interpreter and a master's degree diploma.

“Besides that, there must be another 3 or 5 interpreters who ascertain the knowledge of the interpreter and one of them should have had a working experience with that interpreter. Another organization is called European Commission Joint Interpreting and Conference Service – JICS which was established in Brussels. The members of which is accepted as follows: firstly, the best of the bests (whose ages must be between 25 and 30) are chosen from every territory and they should have a three-year experience together with a diploma except bachelor degree. Afterwards, there will be an examination and an interview. It is not UN which has the most skillful simultaneous interpreters, actually, it is EU because the number of interpreters hired by this organization amounts 500 people. And EU mostly pays attention to the fluency and quality of the simultaneous interpreters” Gile, Daniel. 2008 [8].

As every profession has pros and cons, simultaneous interpretation possesses several advantages and disadvantages, which proves the difficult and easy sides of this profession. Most people argue why simultaneous interpretation is more widely-used than consecutive interpretation. According to the notes by Yagi, S.M, [9] we look into why simultaneous interpretation has more advantages than consecutive interpretation. It has the following advantages:

1) The speech of a certain speaker is conducted without any pauses. This enables speakers to keep the attention of listeners constantly and it enables to sense the reaction and feelings of listeners.

2) The period of time spent on conferences will not be too long thanks to simultaneous interpretation.

3) As foreign languages are developing rapidly, participants of conferences would like to listen to the speeches of speakers in a foreign language. On the contrary, if the speech is conducted in a consecutive interpretation, it will become very boring and time-consuming.

In its turn, simultaneous interpretation has the following disadvantages:

- 1) The cost of hiring simultaneous interpreters and renting the necessary equipment is much higher than consecutive interpretation.
- 2) Two or more than three simultaneous interpreters who know the thematic topic very well are required to invite.
- 3) During simultaneous interpretation, the process of losing main idea and delivering small amount of information happens.

Based on the views provided by Kahneman, Daniel [10], the preparation and anticipating the speaker during simultaneous interpretation provides a very successfully accomplished work. Therefore, it is much more appropriate to pay a close attention to these above mentioned principles. Moreover, they are considered as one of the most impartial advantages in simultaneous interpretation. Consistently good performance in conference interpreting depends on sustained mental alertness. An interpreter must maintain attention and concentration through many hours of meetings and absorb the contents of lengthy discussions on many subjects. This means keeping fit, notably by getting enough sleep and following good habits of nutrition and exercise. An interpreter must also adopt an attitude of intellectual modesty and willingness to learn, keeping up with changes in his or her languages as well current events and the related jargon. Interpreters must be able to understand and clearly state a wide range of possible ideas and arguments representing different sides of any issue, even arguments which may seem implausible, or with which they may strongly disagree. Gaining familiarity with the subject matter to be discussed at an upcoming assignment is important, and attending a meeting in advance will be especially helpful to get a grasp of procedural rules and terms. Careful observation of speakers' gestures and demeanor, as well as the reactions of listeners, will provide additional clues to the intent behind the words. Knowing the specific themes of a conference in advance and obtaining a copy of the agenda, background documents, list of speakers, and any prepared speeches available can also be very helpful.

Many speakers prepare their speeches well in advance of delivery and will gladly give or send a copy to an interpreter who takes the trouble to ask for it. Copies of formal speeches and policy statements by public officials can often be readily obtained from their offices or looked up on their Internet web sites. Sometimes a translation of the speech to be delivered will also be made available by the speaker or his institution (known among interpreters as “a Van Doren”) and can be read out by the interpreter if the translation is of good quality. Yet, despite those elementary precautions,

every speech still has its surprises. A speaker may change his or her mind at the last minute, discard or amend prepared remarks, and say something quite unexpected. (Be especially alert to this when the speech is marked “Check against Delivery”.) And even an experienced interpreter can be caught off guard by a novel idea, an unusual turn of phrase, a breakthrough in the debate, an eccentric speaker, a spur-of-the-moment argument, an impenetrable accent, a mispronounced key word, a halting delivery, poor sound quality, an obscure reference or acronym, or a deliberately ornate way of saying a perfectly simple thing. Overcoming problems of that kind involves a certain amount of intuition. Although an interpreter should avoid wild guesses, it is often possible, relying on the context, to “fill in the blanks” of a statement when an element of it is unclear or indistinctly heard. It can be helpful if one tries, by an effort of imagination, to anticipate what the speaker is likely to say, how he or she is likely to say it, and how it can be made comprehensible to the audience for which one is interpreting. There are times when “words fail”. But an interpreter does not have the luxury to pause, catch her breath, and grope for another word. At such times, one way out is to convey the main thrust of the intended message not through words but through intonation. To sharpen your sense of how your own voice carries different feelings, read out the following “neutral” sentences into your tape recorder, coloring the statement with each of the feelings listed beside it; take a short break, then listen to your performance and consider how well the feeling was conveyed.

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